

Electrochemical Behaviour of *N'*-Benzoyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)pyrazoles

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Manuscript received 20 February 1989, revised 6 June 1989, accepted 21 June 1989

The electrochemical behaviour of *N'*-benzoyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)pyrazoles are studied in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH-2 to 10.10) containing 10% (v/v) dimethylformamide, using polarographic, voltammetric and millicoulometric methods. All the compounds exhibited a well-defined 2-electron reduction wave at DME and a well-defined cathodic peak at HMDE. A plausible mechanism has been suggested on the basis of number of protons and electrons involved in the reduction process. The effect of organic co-solvent and double layer effect on the electrode process have been discussed.

THERE has been a growing interest in the electrochemical behaviour of the pyrazoles, pyrazolines and isoxazoles due to their wide use in medicinal chemistry¹⁻⁵. Some of the pyrazoles have been found to possess anticancer property⁶. Keeping this in view, the electrochemical behaviour of some substituted-benzeneazopyrazoles have been studied at DME and at HMDE and the results are reported.

1; R = H, 2; R = 4'-Cl, 3; R = 4'-Br, 4; R = 2,5'-dimethyl, 5; R = 4'-SO₂NH₂, 6; R = 2',4'-dimethyl

Experimental

The 4-substituted-*N'*-benzoyl-3,5-diphenyl-(benzeneazo)pyrazoles (1-6) were prepared according to the reported method⁷ and were purified by repeated recrystallisation and by tlc. Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2.10-10.10) were prepared⁸. Stock solutions of the substituted-benzeneazopyrazoles (1 × 10⁻³ M) were prepared in dimethylformamide, purified by distilling over P₂O₅⁹. Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide, sodium lauryl sulphate, triton X-100, tween-20 and gelatin were used to study the effect of the surfactants on the polarographic reduction and their solutions prepared in double-distilled water.

Polarography: Polarographic *i*-*V* curves were recorded with Elico CL-25 DC polarograph; the

capillary having the following characteristics in H₂O open circuit: 1.80 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/3} at *h* = 80 cm.

Cyclic voltammetry: The cyclic voltammeter consisted of a RE 0074 X-Y recorder, PAR 173 potentiostat and PAR 175 universal programmer. A PAR 303 SMDE single compartment cell with silver wire as reference electrode and platinum wire as counter electrode was used. A hanging mercury (SMDE 303) drop electrode with drop area of 0.0096 cm² was used as the working cathode.

Millicoulometry: The millicoulometer described by Devris and Kroon¹⁰ using a mercury pool cathode was employed for determining the number of electrons (*n*). The value of *n* was determined using the formula,

$$n_2 = n_1 \left(\frac{\Delta_{id, cad}}{i_{d, cad}} \right) \left(\frac{i_{d, sub}}{\Delta_{id, sub}} \right) \frac{V_1 C_1}{V_2 C_2}$$

where *i*_d and Δ_{id} are the diffusion current and the change in the diffusion current of the polarograms obtained, when the experimental solution (solution to be investigated for the number of electrons) is subjected to polarography. *n*₁ and *n*₂ are the number of electrons involved in the reduction of cadmium ions and substrate respectively. The value of *n* was found to be 2 by comparison with CdSO₄ in Britton-Robinson buffers of pH 4.10 and 8.10 containing 60% (v/v) dimethylformamide. The results are presented in Table 4.

Procedure: Britton-Robinson buffer (7 ml), DMF (10 ml) necessary to keep the compounds in solution, 1M potassium chloride (1.0 ml) and stock solution of *N'*-benzoylarylazopyrazole (2 ml) are mixed thoroughly in the wider limb of H-cell. Deaeration was effected by passing pure nitrogen gas for about 15 min and the polarograms were

TABLE 1 - EFFECT OF pH (BRITTON - ROBINSON BUFFERS) ON $E_{1/2}$ AND WAVE-HEIGHTS OF THE PYRAZOLES (1 - 6)

Pyrazoles = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide = 60% (v/v)

pH	Half-wave potentials (v) vs S.C.E.						Wave heights (μA)					
	1	2	3	4	5	6	1	2	3	4	5	6
2.10	0.62	0.58	0.55	0.65	0.52	0.55	2.4	2.7	2.6	2.4	2.3	3.0
3.10	0.68	0.65	0.64	0.72	0.59	0.62	2.4	2.4	2.5	2.2	2.5	2.8
4.10	0.73	0.71	0.69	0.79	0.67	0.70	2.6	2.2	2.4	2.2	2.3	2.8
5.10	0.79	0.79	0.77	0.85	0.72	0.77	2.5	2.4	2.2	2.3	2.3	2.4
6.10	0.88	0.87	0.86	0.94	0.81	0.85	2.4	2.5	2.3	2.2	2.3	2.5
7.10	0.96	0.93	0.91	0.99	0.88	0.91	2.3	2.6	2.4	2.4	2.4	2.6
8.10	1.03	0.99	0.98	1.03	0.95	0.96	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.2	2.4	2.3
9.10	1.03	0.99	0.98	1.03	0.95	0.95	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.2	2.4	2.3
10.10	1.03	0.99	0.98	1.03	0.95	0.95	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.2	2.4	2.3

TABLE 2

The pyrazoles = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide = 60% (v/v), pH = 4.10

Compd. no.	Sweep rate Vs^{-1}	$-E_{pc}$ v	i_{pc} μA
1	0.020	0.77	0.40
	0.050	0.78	0.55
	0.100	0.80	1.30
	0.200	0.83	1.75
2	0.020	0.74	0.45
	0.050	0.74	0.95
	0.100	0.77	1.55
	0.200	0.80	2.15
3	0.020	0.71	0.60
	0.050	0.72	1.15
	0.100	0.76	1.75
	0.200	0.79	2.35
4	0.020	0.81	0.50
	0.050	0.81	1.10
	0.100	0.84	1.75
	0.200	0.87	2.30
5	0.020	0.69	0.55
	0.050	0.70	1.05
	0.100	0.73	1.65
	0.200	0.76	2.20
6	0.020	0.73	0.60
	0.050	0.73	1.05
	0.100	0.77	1.65
	0.200	0.79	2.20

TABLE 3

The pyrazoles = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, Medium : aqueous demethylformamide = 60% (v/v), pH = 8.10

Compd. no.	Sweep rate Vs^{-1}	$-E_{pc}$ v	i_{pc} μA
1	0.020	1.06	0.55
	0.050	1.07	0.85
	0.100	1.10	1.40
	0.200	1.13	1.95
2	0.020	1.01	0.55
	0.050	1.01	1.20
	0.100	1.04	1.80
	0.200	1.07	2.40
3	0.020	1.01	0.55
	0.050	1.01	1.20
	0.100	1.04	1.80
	0.200	1.06	2.25
4	0.020	1.06	0.60
	0.050	1.06	1.25
	0.100	1.09	1.90
	0.200	1.12	2.25
5	0.020	0.98	0.60
	0.050	0.98	1.25
	0.100	1.01	1.90
	0.200	1.04	2.30
6	0.020	0.98	1.05
	0.050	0.99	1.15
	0.100	1.02	1.75
	0.200	1.05	2.30

recorded. The temperature coefficient was determined by Nejedly¹¹ method. Results are presented in Tables 1 - 6.

Results and Discussion

Polarography: In the pH range (2.10 - 10.10) studied, the compounds are reduced in a single 2-electron reduction wave and this is assigned to the reduction of exocyclic azo group. The wave height is practically independent of pH in the pH range studied. Semi-logarithmic analysis¹² at the different pH values indicates that the wave is irreversible in

TABLE 4 - MILLICOULOMETRIC DATA OF *N'*-(BENZOYL-3,5-DIPHENYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED-BENZENAZO)-PYRAZOLES AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Depolariser concn. = 1.0 ml M^{-2} , Volume = 0.5 ml

pH	Current μA	t s	n
4.10	2.6	0	-
	2.1	7 200	1.8
8.10	2.5	0	-
	2.1	7 200	2.0

TABLE 5 - EFFECT OF ORGANIC CO-SOLVENT ON $E_{1/2}$

The pyrazoles = $1 \times 10^{-3} M$, pH = 4.10 and 8.10

Compd. no.	pH 4.10 $-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs S.C.E. 80%			pH 8.10 $-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs S.C.E. 80%		
	DMF	DMSO	CH ₃ CN	DMF	DMSO	CH ₃ CN
1	0.80	0.72	0.76	1.10	1.01	1.06
2	0.76	0.69	0.72	1.06	0.95	0.99
3	0.74	0.70	0.71	1.04	0.98	1.01
4	0.84	0.75	0.79	1.14	1.05	1.09
5	0.73	0.65	0.69	1.02	0.92	0.97
6	0.75	0.68	0.71	1.01	0.94	0.97

TABLE 6 - EFFECT OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS ON MAXIMA OF *N*'-BENZOYL-3,5-DIPHENYL-4-(BENZENEAZO)PYRAZOLES

Medium : aqueous dimethylformamide = 60% (v/v)

Surfactant	[Surfactant]	$-E_{1/2}$ (V) vs S.C.E.	Wave-height μA
Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide	3×10^{-3}	0.75	2.40
	4×10^{-3}	0.79	1.90
	5×10^{-3}	0.83	1.30
Sodium lauryl sulphate	3×10^{-3}	0.73	2.60
	4×10^{-3}	0.77	1.90
	5×10^{-3}	0.81	1.20
Triton X-100	3×10^{-3}	0.75	2.70
	4×10^{-3}	0.79	2.00
	5×10^{-3}	0.83	1.40
Tween-20	3×10^{-3}	0.72	2.70
	4×10^{-3}	0.76	2.10
	5×10^{-3}	0.79	1.50
Gelatin	3×10^{-3}	0.75	2.30
	4×10^{-3}	0.78	1.60
	5×10^{-3}	0.82	1.10

*Concentration of surfactant just sufficient to eliminate the maxima.

nature. This fact is further confirmed by the shift in half-wave potential towards more negative values with increase in the concentration of the depolariser. The variation of limiting current with mercury column height at different pH values indicates that the wave is diffusion controlled. The independence of limiting current with increase of pH is a further confirmation of the diffusion nature of the wave. Literature survey¹³ reveals that azobenzene undergoes reduction reversibly at low pH values and at low concentrations. Seemingly our compounds represent the reduction at $-N=N-$ except for the fact that we get the irreversible wave. This difference in the behaviour of the azo group may be attributed to the bulky pyrazole group at the end of $-N=N-$ group¹⁴. The half-wave potentials of the compounds are dependent on pH and shift

towards more negative values with increase in pH. $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots are linear upto pH 7.10, and beyond pH 7, the plots show significantly small slopes. Even though half-wave potentials are pH dependent, the limiting current is pH-independent. It is therefore concluded that both the acidic and basic forms of the compounds reaching electrode surface are electro-active. The proton transfer reaction probably precedes the electrode process in cases where $E_{1/2}$ is dependent on pH. Out of the two general sequences¹⁵ for the proton and electron addition, viz.. H^+ , e^- , H^+ , e^- and H^+ , e^- , e^- , H^+ , the latter sequence seems more probable for the compounds in the light of their structural features. The mechanistic steps finds support from the dependence of $E_{1/2}$ on pH. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ in alkaline solutions is not so marked as in the acidic pH range. Infact $E_{1/2}$ becomes practically constant. This constancy may be due to the fact that both the acidic and basic forms of the depolariser are electro-active. However, their half-wave potentials are so close to each other that these waves merge¹⁵ and a single wave appears. The number of electrons involved in the reduction are two and the number of protons involved in the rate-determining step is one. Similar reduction steps have been proposed by others¹⁶⁻²⁰.

Effect of solvent : The data presented in Table 5 suggest that increase in the organic co-solvent percentage beyond 60% (v/v) shifts the half-wave potential towards more negative values. This may be attributed to the following reasons. (i) rise in pH of the medium^{21,22} (with increase in organic co-solvent content), (ii) increase in the dissociation constant of the protonated species²³ and (iii) adsorption of solvent molecules on the electrode surface and this either displaces the depolariser from the electrode surface or makes the electron exchange difficult ; similar behaviour has also been reported in other azo compounds.

Effect of surfactant : The data relating to the effect of surfactant concentration on the polarographic behaviour of the benzeneazopyrazoles reveal that both ionic and non-ionic surfactants suppress the maxima completely. Further addition of surfactant after the complete suppression point is reached, results in the shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative values and suppresses the limiting current. This may be attributed to the preferential adsorption of the surfactant at DME, which in turn causes the partial desorption of the depolariser from the electrode surface and lowers the surface concentration²⁴ of

Fig. 1. Polarograms of the pyrazoles ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in aqueous dimethylformamide (60%, v/v) at pH 4.10.

the depolariser. The structure of the double-layer²⁵ is also affected by adsorption of the surfactant. These effects would result in a decrease in the rate of electrode process and shift in half-wave potentials towards more negative values.

Cyclic voltammetry: The results obtained in the cyclic voltammetric study of the compounds is shown in Tables 2 and 3. Typical cyclic voltammetric curves obtained with *N'*-benzoyl-3,5-diphenyl-4-(substituted-benzeneazo)pyrazoles are shown in Fig. 1. The absence of anodic peak in reverse scan in the irreversible nature of the electrode process. The plot of i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ suggests the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction process. The variation in i_{pc} and E_{pc} values with pH is similar to that observed in polarographic studies (Fig. 2). This is expected since the peak in CVM is generally similar to the half-wave potential observed in polarographic studies.

Substituent effects: The near equality of the values of α_n and $dE_{1/2}/d_{pH}$ for the compounds studied confirms that the compounds are undergoing reduction by the same mechanism. Hence the Hammett plots are constructed between $E_{1/2}$ and σ . The positive (ρ) value observed in the present investigations suggest that electron addition is important in the reduction process. The value of specific reaction constant (ρ) for the wave of the azo

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of *N'*-benzoyl-3,2-diphenyl-4-(benzeneazo)pyrazole ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in aqueous dimethylformamide (60%, v/v) at pH 4.10 and 8.10.

group is found to be 0.19, which is in good agreement with the values reported in the literature²⁰ for similar systems.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of S. K. University, for facilities.

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